

E. V. Sid

*State Institution «Zaporizhia medical academy of post-graduate education Ministry of health of Ukraine»
Zaporizhzhia, Ukraine*

Є. В. Сідь

*Державний заклад «Запорізька медична академія післядипломної освіти Міністерства охорони здоров'я України»
Запоріжжя, Україна*

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF GERIATRIC PATIENTS SEEKING EMERGENCY MEDICAL CARE

Психологічні особливості геріатричних пацієнтів, що звертаються за екстреною медичною допомогою

Abstract

The increase of people's lifetime leads to an increase among the number of geriatric patients in world. This determines the increased interest of general practitioners to the issues of gerontology and geriatrics. Atherosclerotic changes of vessels are overlaid with discirculatory encephalopathy, which leads to disruption of the brain geriatric patients. The disorder among cognitive and mnesic functions affects the quality of the complaints and anamnesis data of while communicating of such patients with medical staff. Most of the work on the diagnosis and treatment of elderly patients in the prehospital stage is on the shoulders of the general practitioner, a field staff of emergency medical service. The doctor in the process of communication with older patient, in order not to make mistakes in diagnostic and tactical relationship, must first establish an active rational interaction with the geriatric patient.

Keywords: *geriatric patient, coronary heart disease, hypertension, prehospital stage.*

Резюме

Зі збільшенням тривалості життя спостерігається зростання чисельності літніх пацієнтів і висока потреба в одержанні ними медичної допомоги, що і визначає підвищений інтерес лікарів загальної практики до питань геронтології та геріатрії. Атеросклеротичні зміни судин обтяжуються дисциркуляторною енцефалопатією, що призводить до порушення роботи мозку геріатричних пацієнтів. Порушення когнітивних і мнестичних функцій впливає на якість скарг і даних анамнезу при спілкуванні таких пацієнтів з медичним персоналом. Велика частина роботи з діагностики та лікування літніх хворих на догоспітальному етапі лягає на плечі лікарів загальної практики, виїзний персонал швидкої медичної допомоги. Лікаряю, в процесі спілкування з літнім пацієнтом, щоб не помилитися в діагностичних і тактичних питаннях, слід, перш за все, встановити активну, раціональну взаємодію з геріатричним пацієнтом.

Ключові слова: *артеріальна гіпертензія, геріатричний пацієнт, догоспітальний етап, ішемічна хвороба серця.*

The increase of people's lifetime leads to an increase among the number of geriatric patients in world. This determines the increased interest of general practitioners to the issues of gerontology and geriatrics. The increase in the number of elderly people is accompanied by changes in situation with health among the population. Without an understanding of the internal psychological structure of the individual geriatric patient, it is impossible to provide emergency medical care to this cohort of patients that requires special training of medical staff of emergency medical service (EMS). Stereotyped communication skills with elderly patients should be developed on the basis of accurate knowledge of the psychological

barriers existing among this age category of patients and special post-graduate training among emergency geriatrics [1, 2].

Atherosclerotic changes of vessels are overlaid with discirculatory encephalopathy, which leads to disruption of the brain geriatric patients. The disorder among cognitive and mnesic functions affects the quality of the complaints and anamnesis data of while communicating of such patients with medical staff. When geriatric patients communicate with the dispatcher of EMS they may pronounce the address, surname, name, patronymic, mistakenly which will affect the timeliness of the arrival of the medical care [3, 4].

Most of the work on the diagnosis and treatment

of elderly patients in the prehospital stage is on the shoulders of the general practitioner, a field staff of EMS. When providing medical care for older patients with cognitive disorders field personnel of SMP are facing some psychological problems, which can be divided into two categories: 1) those that don't depend on professional training of the physician and 2) the ones dependent on psychological literacy and professionalism of the visiting medical staff [5, 6].

The first category includes the following: the problem of evaluation of own health by the geriatric patient and the timeliness of his access to medical care: the problem of communication with the medical staff in terms of presenting their complaints; the problem of the correct behavior with the intent of preventing life-threatening complications before the arrival of medical personnel. The second category of problems completely depends on professionalism among the field of medical ethics and deontology. This is a problem of proper psychological interaction with the personality of an elderly patient with the help verbal and non-verbal communication technique with the purpose of finding rational ways of active interaction with the patient [7, 8].

Micro- and macrostructural changes of the brain associated with aging, contribute to the emergence of psychosomatic disorders among the elderly. Psychosomatic diseases (gr. psyche – the soul, somatic – the body) is due to psychogenic disorders of internal organs or physiological systems (circulatory, respiratory, digestive, etc.). Temporal cortex, thalamus and cerebellum undergo major changes in terms of reduction in temporal gray matter as we age. These structural changes are closely correlated with behavioral changes among the elderly. The elderly psychosomatic disorders are frequent diseases, whose manifestations among this age group have their differences. The main substrate of such differences is considered as the neurophysiological and psychological changes in the body associated with aging. Awareness of these age peculiarities of the pathogenesis of psychosomatic diseases is the basis of successful treatment. The detection rate of psychosomatic disorders among geriatric patients is quite high and ranges from 40–45% [9, 10, 11].

Disorders of the body which are psychosomatic in nature are often found among patients with cardiovascular disease, affecting the course of the underlying disease. Acute stressful situation (man-made disaster, natural disasters) as well as chronic stress (everyday psycho-emotional stress) can be a risk factor for development of acute cardiac pathology. Arterial hypertension and ischemic heart disease are the most frequent nosology that geriatric patients apply make to seek emergency medical care [12, 13].

The relationship of hypertension with various

psycho-emotional disorders and personality characteristics of patients were shown in several papers in the 60–70s of the last century. One of the most characteristic psychological features of patients with hypertension is a high level of anxiety [14, 15].

It is known that the sets of identity and position of a person in his professional and family environment affect circulatory function and its physiological regulation. In this regard, particularly relevant is the study of the psychological characteristics of people with hypertension. It should be noted that psychopathological disorders of the neurotic level are found among 45–80% of patients with arterial hypertension. Mental changes in the development of hypertensive crisis vary and depend on the characteristics of the individual patient, the severity of hypertension. The most common psychopathological syndromes should include anxious, hypochondriac, neurasthenic and depressive. Timely detection and correction of these disorders allow achieving the therapeutic effect faster in the provision of emergency medical care [16, 17].

Geriatric patients with arterial hypertension with anxiety syndrome often turn to emergency medical service, as a hypertensive crisis occurs they have symptoms typical for neurotic disorders. This affects the course of the disease, the effectiveness of the emergency medical care provision at hypertensive crisis, patients' quality of life, and interaction with a staff of EMS or a general practitioner. Mental changes that cause the emotional reaction of the person become inactive; he has a tendency to «loop» on some bad experiences that create the conditions for high blood pressure. Thus, the vicious circle of psychosomatic diseases is observed: mental disorders lead to physical disorders, which, in turn, complicate and burden of mental manifestations among geriatric patients [18, 19].

The possible mechanisms of somatic deregulation referring to among psychosomatic diseases, the suppression mechanisms of self-regulation of the autonomic nervous system with the occurrence of its relative independence from the state of the higher nervous activity. Aspects of temperament, such as low sensitivity threshold to stimuli, high intensity of reactions to external stimuli, difficulties of adaptation to new experiences with a predominance of negative emotions may also be responsible for high risk of psychosomatic disorders [20, 21].

Anxiety quite often is accompanied by vegetative symptoms, which carries mainly polysystemic character. Cardiac symptoms can dominate: palpitations, interruptions in heart work, cardialgia and lability of blood pressure level. Patients complain of a feeling of lack of air, shortness of breath, difficulty breathing,

dizziness, headache, feeling of fever or chills, tremor, paresthesia. Thus, despite the large number of complaints of somatic nature that are applied by these patients to the doctor, even the most careful examination does not correspond to the severity of the disease and the stated complaints [22, 23].

In the development of hypertension asthenic symptoms can be observed: irritability, insomnia, more fatigue, headaches. Among some geriatric patients an obsessive concern for their health appears, sometimes hysterical reaction quickly form, which leads to frequent, sometimes unreasonable treatment on EMS. With the progression of hypertension psycho-organic disorders are increasing: exhaustion, fatigue, memory disorder, mood swings. Because of this the geriatric patients become touchy, attach great importance to worldly troubles [24, 25].

Among people of older age groups there are often diseases of coronary artery that are the leading cause of death. With age not only the frequency of coronary heart disease (CHD) increases, but the clinical picture of the disease also changed. Knowledge of the characteristics of the clinic ischemic heart disease among patients of elderly and senile age is of particular relevance and importance. It also should be noted that CHD has a significant impact on the patients' health condition; it requires compulsory treatment and emergency medical care when becoming a risk factor of fatal complications. Enumerating well-known etiological factors of coronary heart disease, you need to focus on the social and biological individuality of a geriatric patient. It should be noted that the mental features of elderly patients have the most powerful influence on the course and prognosis of CHD: patients establish relationships worse with people including a doctor and are less adequate in social interaction; they are not always able to perform daily chores, cannot cope with problems in the family, do not adhere to medical regimen [26, 27].

Depression is not uncommon among people with coronary heart disease, 22–33% of patients suffer from depression after cardiac events. Among CHD patients, depression is connected with reduction

in short-term and long-term survival. According to the study, Barefoot J. C. et al. concluded that patients with coronary heart disease combined with depression have a higher risk of mortality than patients without depression. The authors suggest that long-term risk can be caused by factors of atherosclerosis, changes in neuroendocrine function, failure to adhere to behavior and lifestyle that are recommended for CHD patients [28, 29].

The closest relationship between age, the beginning of mental disorders and newly diagnosed CHD was observed among men with progressive angina whose appearance of psychopathological disorders preceded the initial diagnosis of CHD on average 4 months earlier. At the same time diagnosis CHD was «late» among patients, whose clinical picture was dominated by symptoms of anxiety, depression and other psychopathological symptoms. Coronary heart disease in such cases was diagnosed at the stage of already developed clinical picture or the development of acute coronary syndrome. Thus, stress and psychopathological reactions, on the one hand, often precede the development of CHD and, on the other hand, worsen it and complicate diagnosis among elderly patients [30, 31].

CONCLUSION

Thus, the doctor in the process of communication with older patient, in order not to make mistakes in diagnostic and tactical relationship, must first establish an active rational interaction with the geriatric patient. The process of communication with elderly patients should be organized by overcoming the psychological barriers it must be thorough, the doctor should understand wordly and social problems of the geriatric patient. Doctor of EMS must remember that psychopathological syndrome can be a burden for hypertension and coronary artery disease. The doctor should remember that the question about the upcoming hospitalization is a powerful stress factor, as it involves the shift from home and long established habitual behavior, and the necessity of existence in the new hospital conditions.

ЛІТЕРАТУРА

1. Соколовская Т. А. Демографические проблемы и состояние здоровья населения пожилого возраста // Геронтология. – 2013. – Т. 1, № 1. – С. 60–71.
2. Каспрук Л. И., Бегун Д. Н., Жакупова Г. Т. и др. Некоторые актуальные аспекты социальной геронтологии // Современные проблемы науки и образования. – 2015. – № 3. – С. 53–61.
3. Шмырев В. И., Васильев А. С., Рудас М. С. Дисциркуляторная энцефалопатия – вопросы патогенеза, диагностики, дифференциальной диагностики и лечения на современном этапе // Кремлевская медицина. Клинический вестник. – 2009. – № 4. – С. 31–36.
4. Гимоян Л. Г., Силванян Г. Г. Нарушение когнитивных функций: актуальность проблемы, факторы риска, возможности профилактики и лечения // Архивъ внутренней медицины. – 2013. – № 2. – С. 35–40.
5. Болотнова Т. В., Юсупов А. Р. Интеграция деятельности медицинских и социальных служб при оказании помощи пожилым // Академический

журнал Западной Сибири. – 2012. – № 3. – С. 6–7.

6. Дегриз Я. М., Фролова Е. В., Тур Е. Ю. Структурированный подход к выявлению потребностей пожилого человека в медицинской помощи // Российский семейный врач. – 2014. – Т. 18. – № 1. – С. 12–19.

7. Фролова Е. В., Корыстина Е. М. Комплексная оценка состояния здоровья пожилого человека и возможности ее осуществления в общей врачебной практике // Российский семейный врач. – 2010. – Т. 14. – № 1. – С. 12–23.

8. Матвейчик Т. В., Вальчук Э. Э., Солдатенкова И. Г. Проблемы первичной медицинской помощи пациентам пожилого и старческого возраста // Вопросы организации и информатизации здравоохранения. – 2011. – № 4. – С. 24–31.

9. Чабан О. С., Хаустова Е. А., Безшейко В. Г. Особенности проявления психосоматических расстройств у лиц пожилого возраста // НейроNEWS. – 2012. – № 2/1. – С. 16–19.

10. Fjell A. M., Westlye L. T., Amlie I. et al. High consistency of regional cortical thinning in aging across multiple samples // *Alm. Cerebral cortex*. – 2009. – Vol. 19. – № 9. – P. 2001–2012.

11. Оленская Т. Л., Прядко Л. В. Скрининговое исследование депрессивных состояний у пожилых людей во время проведения массовой медико-профилактической акции в концепции гериатрических синдромов // Фундаментальные исследования. – 2013. – № 9. – С. 715–719.

12. Лазарева Е. Ю., Николаев Е. Л. Психосоматические соотношения при кардиальной патологии: современные направления исследований // Вестник Чувашского университета. – 2012. – № 3. – С. 429–435.

13. Горбачева С. М., Салато О. В. «Боль в грудной клетке» на догоспитальном этапе // Бюллетень Восточно-Сибирского научного центра Сибирского отделения Российской академии медицинских наук. – 2012. – № 4 – С. 220–226.

14. Ланг Г. Ф. Гипертоническая болезнь и центральная нервная система / Л.: Медицина, 1975. – С. 37–53.

15. Анохин П. К. Эмоциональные напряжения как предпосылка к развитию неврогенных заболеваний сердечно-сосудистой системы // Вестн. АМН СССР. – 1967. – № 6. – С. 10–18.

16. Громова Е. А. Психосоциальные факторы риска сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний (обзор литературы) // Сибирский медицинский журнал. – 2012. – № 2. – С. 22–29.

17. Ениколопов С. Тревога и гипертоническая болезнь. Порочный круг // Украинський ревматологічний журнал. – 2008. – №. 2. – С. 27–28.

18. Глезер М. Г. Гендерные особенности и лечение артериальной гипертензии у людей пожилого возраста // Клиническая геронтология. –

2012. – № 5–6. – С. 3–10.

19. Табеева Г. Р. Когнитивные и некогнитивные расстройства у пациентов пожилого возраста, ассоциированные со стрессом // Неврология, нейропсихиатрия, психосоматика. – 2015. – № 1. – С. 87–93.

20. Колесников Д. Б., Рапопорт С. И., Вознесенская Л. А. Современные взгляды на психосоматические заболевания // Клиническая медицина. – 2014. – Т. 92. – № 7. – С. 12–18.

21. Исмагилов М. Ф. Вегетативная конституция, нарушения равновесия вегетативной нервной системы, синдром вегетативной дисфункции // Неврологический вестник. – 2014. – № 4. – С. 91–96.

22. Ватутин Н. Т., Христинченко М. А., Картамышева Е. В. и др. Тревожные расстройства и сердечно-сосудистые заболевания // Кровообіг та гемостаз. – 2013. – № 2. – С. 72–79.

23. Нуралиева Н. Ф., Напалков Д. А. Депрессия и сердечно-сосудистые заболевания // Вестник Российской академии медицинских наук. – 2014. – № 9–10. – С. 21–26.

24. Корнацкий В. М., Третьяк И. В., Чаплинская В. В. Особливості емоційного стану пацієнтів з артеріальною гіпертензією // Український кардіологічний журнал. – 2011. – №. 3. – С. 55–59.

25. Куличенко Л. Л., Ивахненко И. В. Характеристика соматической патологии у людей пожилого и старческого возраста // Волгоградский научно-медицинский журнал. – 2012. – № 1. – С. 88–90.

26. Дядыка А. И., Багрий А. Э. Сердечно-сосудистые заболевания у пожилых / К.: «Люди в белом», 2013. – 170 с.

27. Прохорович Е. А. Особенности фармакотерапии ишемической болезни сердца в пожилом возрасте // Медицинский совет. – 2012. – № 2. – С. 12–16.

28. Киселева М. Г. Психологические факторы и течение сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний // Национальный психологический журнал – 2012. – № 1. – С. 124–130.

29. Barefoot J. C., Schroll M. Symptoms of depression, acute myocardial infarction, and total mortality in a community sample // *Circulation*. – 1996. – Vol. 11. – P. 1976–1980.

30. Гарганеева Н. П. Новая стратегия многофакторной профилактики сердечно-сосудистых заболеваний у пациентов с тревожными и депрессивными расстройствами в условиях психосоциального стресса // Русский медицинский журнал. – 2008. – № 25. – С. 1704–1711.

31. Мкртчян В. Р., Бенделиани Н. Г., Кожокова Л. З. Тревога и депрессия в патогенезе атеросклероза и ишемической болезни сердца // Бюллетень НЦССХ им. А. Н. Бакулева РАМН. Сердечно-сосудистые заболевания. – 2014. – Т. 15. – № 2. – С. 10–16.

REFERENCE

1. Sokolovskaya T. A. (2013) Demograficheskie problem i sostoyanie zdorovya naseleniya pozhilogo vozrasta [Demographic challenges and the health status of the population aged]. *Gerontologiya*, vol. 1, no 1, pp. 60–71.
2. Kaspruk L. I., Begun D. N., Zhakupova G. T., Snasapova D. M. (2015) Nekotore aktualnie aspekty sotsialnoi gerontologii [Some relevant aspects of social gerontology]. *Sovremennye problem nauki i obrazovaniya*, no 3, pp. 53–61.
3. Shmirev V. I., Vasilev A. S., Rudas M. S. (2014) Distsikulyatornaya entsefalopatiya – voprosi patogeneza, diagnostiki, differentsialnoi diagnostiki i lecheniya na sovremennom etape [Discirculatory encephalopathy – the issues pathogenesis, diagnosis, differential diagnosis and treatment at the present stage]. *Kremlevskaya meditsina. Klinicheskii vestnik*, no 4, pp. 31–36.
4. Gimoyan L. G., Silvanyan G. G. (2013) Narushenie kognitivnykh funktsii: aktualnost' problemi, faktori riska, vozmozhnosti profilaktiki i lecheniya [Violation of cognitive functions: relevance problems, risk factors, possibilities of prevention and treatment]. *Arhiv vnutrennei meditsini*, no 2, pp. 35–40.
5. Bolotnova T. V., Yusupov A. R. (2012) Integratsiya deyatelnosti meditsinskikh i sotsialnykh sluzhb pri okazanii pomoschi pozhilim [Integrating medical and social services assistance to the elderly]. *Akademicheskii zhurnal Zapadnoi Sibiri*, no 3, pp. 6–7.
6. Degriz Ya. M., Frolova E. V., Tur E. Yu. (2014) Strukturirovannii podhod k viyavleniyu potrebnosti pozhilogo cheloveka v meditsinskoj pomoschi [The structured approach to the determining of the old and elderly patients' needs in medical care]. *Russian family doctor*, vol. 18, no 1, pp. 12–19.
7. Frolova E. V., Koristina E. M. (2010) Kompleksnaya otsenka sostoyaniya zdorovya pozhilogo cheloveka i vozmozhnosti ee osuschestvleniya v obschei vrachebnoy praktike [Comprehensive geriatric assessment in general practice. is it possible?]. *Russian family doctor*, vol. 14, no 1, pp. 12–23.
8. Matveichik T. V., Valchuk E. E., Soldatenkova I. G. (2011) Problemy pervichnoi meditsinskoj pomoschi patsientam pozhilogo i starcheskogo vozrasta [Problems of rendering primary medical care to patients of middle and old age]. *Problems of public health organization and informatization*, no 4, pp. 24–31.
9. Chaban O. S., Haustova E. A., Bezsheiko V. G. (2012) Osobennosti proyavleniya psichosomaticheskikh rasstroystv u lits pozhilogo vozrasta [Peculiarities of psychosomatic disorders in the elderly]. *Neiro NEWS*, no 2/1, pp. 16–19.
10. Fjell A. M., Westlye L. T., Amlie I. et al. (2009) High consistency of regional cortical thinning in aging across multiple samples. *Cerebral cortex*, vol. 19, no 9, pp. 2001–2012. doi.org/10.1093/cercor/bhn232
11. Olenskaya T. L., Pryadko L. V. (2013) Skringingovoe issledovanie depressivnykh sostoyanii u pozhilih lyudei vo vremya provedeniya massovoi mediko-profilakticheskoi aktsii v kontseptsii geriatricheskikh sindromov [Screening research of depressions at elderly people during carrying out the mass medico-preventive action in the concept of geriatric syndromes]. *Fundamental research*, no 9, pp. 715–719.
12. Lazareva E. Yu., Nikolaev E. L. (2012) Psichosomaticheskie sootnosheniya pri kardialnoi patologii: sovremennye napravleniya issledovaniya [Psychosomatic interrelations in cardiac pathology: current research trends]. *Vestnik Chuvashskogo universiteta*, no 3, pp. 429–435.
13. Gorbacheva S. M., Salato O. V. (2012) «Bol v grudnoi kletke» na dogospitalnom etape [«Chest pain» at pre-hospital stage]. *Bulletin of the East Siberian Scientific Center SBRAMS*, vol. 86, no 4, pp. 220–226.
14. Lang G. F. (1975) Gipertonicheskaya bolezn i tsentranaya nervnaya sistema. Izbrannie trudy [Hypertension and central nervous system. Selected works]. Leningrad: Meditsina, pp. 37–53, (in Russia).
15. Anohin P. K. (1967) Emotsionalnye napryazheniya kak predposilka k razvitiyu nevrogennykh zabolovaniy serdechno-sosudistoi sistemi [Emotional stress as a prerequisite to the development of neurogenic diseases of the cardiovascular system]. *Vestnik Akademii nauk SSSR*, no 6, pp. 10–18.
16. Gromova E. A. (2012) Psichosotsialnye faktori riska serdechno-sosudistikh zabolovaniy (obzor literaturi) [Psychosocial factors risk of cardiovascular diseases (review of the literature)]. *Sibirskii meditsinskii zhurnal*, vol. 27, no 2, pp. 22–29.
17. Enikolopov S. (2008) Trevoga i gipertonicheskaya bolezn. Porochnii krug [Anxiety and hypertonic disease. Vicious circle]. *Ukrainiskii revmatologicheskii zhurnal*, vol. 32, no 2, pp. 27–28.
18. Glezer M. G. (2012) Gendernie osobennosti i lechenie arterialnoi gipertenzii u lyudei pozhilogo vozrasta [Gender and the treatment of hypertension in the elderly]. *Clinical gerontology*, no 5–6, pp. 3–10.
19. Tabeeva G. R. (2015) Kognitivnye i nekognitivnye rasstroystva u patsientov pozhilogo vozrasta, assotsirovannye so stressom [Stress-related cognitive and non-cognitive impairments in elderly patients]. *Nevrologiya, neiropsihiatriya*,

psihosomatika, vol. 7, no 1, pp. 87–93.

20. Kolesnikov D. B., Rapoport S. I., Voznesenskaya L. A. (2014) Sovremennie vzglyadi na psihosomaticheskie zabolevaniya [Current views of psychosomatic diseases]. Clinical medicine, vol. 92, no 7, pp. 12–18.

21. Ismagilov M. F. (2014) Vegetativnaya konstitutsiya, narusheniya ravnovesiya vegetativnoi nervnoyi stemi, sindrom vegetativnoi disfunktsii [Autonomic constitution, disbalance of autonomic nervous system, autonomic dysfunction syndrome]. Nevrologicheskii vestnik, vol. 46, no 4, pp. 91–96.

22. Vatutin N. T., Hristichenko M. A., Kartamisheva E. V., Keting E. V. (2013) Trevozhnie rasstroistva i serdechnososudistie zabolevaniya [Anxiety disorders and cardiovascular disease]. Krovoobih ta hemostaz, no 2, pp. 72–79.

23. Nuralieva N. F., Napalkov D. A. (2014) Depressiya i serdechno-sosudistie zabolevaniya [Depression and Cardiovascular Diseases]. Annals of the Russian academy of medical science, vol. 69, no 9–10, pp. 21–26.

24. Kornatskii V. M., Tretyak I. V., Chaplinska V. V. (2011) Osoblyvosti emotsiynoho stanu patsiyentiv z arterialnoyu hipertenziiyeyu [Features of the emotional state of patients with arterial hypertension]. Ukrainian Cardiology Journal, no 3, pp. 55–59.

25. Kulichenko L. L., Ivahnenko I. V. (2012) Harakteristika somaticheskoi patologii u lyude ipozhilogo i starcheskogo vozrasta [Characteristic of somatic disease in the elderly and senile]. Volgogradskii nauchno-meditsinskii zhurnal, no 1, pp. 88–90.

26. Dadik A. I., Bagrii A. E. (2013) Serdechno-sosudistie zabolevaniya u pozhilih [Cardiovascular disease in the elderly]. Moskva: Meditsina, pp. 137–139, (in Russia).

27. Prohorovich E. A. (2012) Osobennosti farmakoterapii ishemicheskoi bolezni serdtsa v pozhilom vozraste [Features of pharmacotherapy of ischemic heart disease in old age]. Meditsinskii sovet, no 2, pp. 12–16.

28. Kiseleva M. G. (2012) Psihologicheskie faktori i techenie serdechno-sosudistih zabolevanii [Psychological factors and course of cardiovascular disease]. Natsionalnii psihologicheskii zhurnal, no 1, pp. 124–130.

29. Barefoot J. C., Schroll M. (1996) Symptoms of depression, acute myocardial infarction, and total mortality in a community sample. Circulation, vol. 93, no 11, pp. 1976–1980.

30. Garganeeva N. P. (2008) Novaya strategiya mnogofaktornoj profilaktiki serdechno-sosudistih zabolevanii u patsiyentov s trevozhnimi i depressivnimi rasstroistvami v usloviyah psihosotsialnogo stressa [New strategy of multifactorial prophylaxis of cardiovascular diseases in patients with anxiety and depressive disorders in conditions of psychosocial stress]. Russian Medical Journal, vol. 16, no. 25, pp. 1704–1711.

31. Mkrtychyan V. R., Bendeliani N. G., Kozhokova L. Z. (2014) Trevoga i depressiya v patogeneze ateroskleroza i ishemicheskoi bolezni serdtsa [Anxiety and Depression in the Pathogenesis of Atherosclerosis and Coronary Heart Disease]. Byulleten NTSSSKH im. A. N. Bakuleva RAMN. Serdechno-sosudistyye zabolevaniya, vol. 15, no 2, pp. 10–16.

Стаття надійшла до редакції 12.11.2017